

Supplemental materials

Supplemental Table S1. *Baseline measurements used for functional grouping of rats*

Baseline Measurement	Week 2		Week 6			
	Healthy Controls (n = 16)	Disease Controls (n = 20)	Healthy Controls (n = 16)	Disease Controls (n = 20)	Prophylactic Tenapanor (n = 20)	Therapeutic Tenapanor (n = 20)
Systolic blood pressure, mmHg	131.4 ± 3.0	138.9 ± 3.7	134.6 ± 4.4	141.2 ± 3.5	136.7 ± 3.8	140.3 ± 3.9
Urinary protein:creatinine ratio	1.56 ± 0.10	1.94 ± 0.17	1.64 ± 0.09	2.20 ± 0.22*	2.10 ± 0.16*	2.19 ± 0.15**
Urinary albumin:creatinine ratio	0.015 ± 0.002	0.134 ± 0.017****	0.014 ± 0.001	0.092 ± 0.013****	0.111 ± 0.016****	0.192 ± 0.035****†
Creatinine clearance, mL/min	2.18 ± 0.06	1.01 ± 0.03****	2.14 ± 0.06	1.06 ± 0.04****	1.05 ± 0.04****	1.05 ± 0.03****
Plasma blood urea nitrogen, mg/dL	15.91 ± 0.59	39.41 ± 0.89****	16.96 ± 0.59	37.38 ± 1.06****	39.76 ± 1.03****	39.02 ± 0.96****
Plasma creatinine, mg/dL	0.388 ± 0.010	0.736 ± 0.015****	0.388 ± 0.006	0.731 ± 0.023****	0.735 ± 0.034****	0.719 ± 0.019****
Body weight, g	351.6 ± 4.5	310.6 ± 3.7****	349.7 ± 4.3	316.2 ± 4.1****	313.8 ± 3.3****	309.8 ± 3.4****

Data are mean ± standard error. * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$ and **** $P < 0.0001$ versus healthy controls within time period; t -test. † $P < 0.05$ versus disease controls within time period; t -test.

Supplemental Figure S1: Effect of tenapanor on urinary (A) sodium and (B) phosphorus levels adjusted against urinary potassium levels. Data are shown as the mean ratio (+ standard error). [†] $P < 0.05$ DC versus HC; [§] $P < 0.05$ Px versus DC; [‡] $P < 0.05$ Tx versus DC; all comparisons within time period, Tukey's multiple comparisons test. DC, disease controls; HC, healthy controls; Px, prophylactic tenapanor; Tx, therapeutic tenapanor.

Supplemental Figure S2: Effect of tenapanor on body weight over time. Data are shown as the mean (+ standard error). $^{\dagger}P < 0.05$ DC versus HC; $^{\S}P < 0.05$ Px versus DC; $^{\ddagger}P < 0.05$ Tx versus DC, all comparisons within the same time period were analysed using 2-way, repeated measures ANOVA with Bonferroni multiple group comparison. DC, disease controls; HC, healthy controls; Px, prophylactic tenapanor; Tx, therapeutic tenapanor.

Supplemental Figure S3: Effect of tenapanor on food intake over time. Data are shown as the mean (+ standard error). * $P < 0.05$ DC (2 week) versus HC (2 week); † $P < 0.05$ DC versus HC; § $P < 0.05$ Px versus DC; ‡ $P < 0.05$ Tx versus DC, Dunnett's multiple comparisons test. DC, disease controls; HC, healthy controls; Px, prophylactic tenapanor; Tx, therapeutic tenapanor.

Supplemental Figure S4: Effect of tenapanor on (A) heart weight per body weight and (B) heart weight per tibia length. Data are shown as the mean (+ standard deviation). **** $P < 0.0001$, Tukey's multiple comparisons test. DC, disease controls; HC, healthy controls; Px, prophylactic tenapanor; Tx, therapeutic tenapanor.